

Compounds of Hexamethylene Tetramine with Complex Cobalt Salts and the Nature of Residual Affinity.

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Hexamethylene tetramine has been found to combine with a large number of salts and acids, both simple and complex, to form molecular or additive compounds. Several investigators have worked on the subject and a complete reference thereto will be found in Ray and Sarkar's paper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 390). The substance has also been employed as a microchemical reagent (Vivario and Wagennar, *Pharm. Weekbl.*, 1917, 54, 157; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1919, 58, 228 ; 1925, 67, 298). Rây and Sarkar (*Mikrochem. Emich Festschrift*, 1930, p. 243) have already shown that magnesium and other alkaline earth salts readily give with several complex metallic cyanides and urotropine characteristic crystals, suitable for microchemical identification of the corresponding alkaline earth element. The composition of these compounds thus formed was not determined by the authors. In the present paper the preparation, properties and the composition of the molecular compounds, formed by urotropine with several simple and double salts of thiosulphato-pentacyano-cobaltic acid, have been described. The alkali and alkaline earth salts of this acid have been prepared by Rây and his co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 325 ; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 853). The compositions of the compounds prepared, together with those of the original salts, are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Original salt.	Compounds with urotropine.	Diff. in H ₂ O mols.
Ba ₂ X, 7.5 H ₂ O	Ba ₂ X, 1.5B, 4.5 H ₂ O	-3
Sr ₂ X, 3.5 H ₂ O	Sr ₂ X, 2B, 7H ₂ O	3.5
Ca ₂ X, 8 H ₂ O	Ca ₂ X, 2B, 8H ₂ O	0
Mg ₂ X, 9.5 H ₂ O	Mg ₂ X, 2B, 12 H ₂ O	2.5
Li ₄ X, 4 H ₂ O	Li ₄ X, 2B, 8 H ₂ O	4
—	BaK ₂ X, 1.5B, 1.5H ₂ O	—
—	SrK ₂ X, 1.5 B	—
—	CaK ₂ X, B, 7 H ₂ O	—
—	MgK ₂ X, 2B, 2.5 H ₂ O	—
—	Li ₂ K ₂ X, 2B	—
—	Ba(NH ₄) ₂ X, 1.5B, 4.5 H ₂ O	—
—	Sr(NH ₄) ₂ X, 1.5B, 2 H ₂ O	—
—	Ca(NH ₄) ₂ X, B, 7H ₂ O	—
—	Mg(NH ₄) ₂ X, 1.5B, 5H ₂ O	—

The double alkali-alkaline earth salts of the complex acid have not been described ; but the addition of urotropine to a solution of the alkali salt of the complex acid in presence of any alkaline earth salt precipitates the compounds of the double alkali-alkaline earth salt of the complex acid with the base. Similar compounds of urotropine with complex ferro- and ferricyanides have been described by Barbieri (*Gazzetta*, 1930, 60, 229). The composition of these compounds as well as of the original complex cyanides are also shown below.

TABLE II.

Original salt.	Compounds with urotropine.	Diff. in H ₂ O mols.
Mg ₂ X, 10H ₂ O	Mg ₂ X, B, 12H ₂ O	2
MgK ₂ X	MgK ₂ X, B, 8H ₂ O	8
Mg(NH ₄)X	Mg(NH ₄) ₂ X, B, 10H ₂ O	10
MgNa ₂ X	MgNa ₂ X, B, 9H ₂ O	9
Sr ₂ X ₂ , 14H ₂ O	Sr ₂ X ₂ , 4B, 20H ₂ O	6
Sr(NH ₄)X, 3H ₂ O	Sr(NH ₄)X, 2B, 5H ₂ O	2
SrKX, 3H ₂ O	SrKX, 2B, 5H ₂ O	2
Ca ₂ X ₂ , 12H ₂ O	Ca ₂ X ₂ , 4B, 20H ₂ O	8
CaKX, 8H ₂ O	CaKX, 2B, 6H ₂ O	8
Ba ₂ X ₂ , 20H ₂ O	Ba ₂ X ₂ , 3B, 18H ₂ O	-2
K ₃ X	K ₃ X, B, 9H ₂ O	9 Rây & Sarkar (loc. cit.)
K ₃ Co(CN) ₆	K ₃ Co(CN) ₆ , B, 6.5 H ₂ O	6.5 ..

An examination of the composition of these compounds with those of the original salts reveals many interesting features regarding the nature of secondary valencies as exhibited in these molecular compounds. In most cases it will be observed that the capacity for association with water molecules for any particular salt increases after combination with hexamethylene tetramine, though one would naturally expect that the satisfaction of residual valencies by the addition of the latter would reduce the number of water molecules in the products formed. The point of association of the hexamine molecules, or, for the matter of that, of water molecules, in the addition

compounds cannot, therefore, be definitely localised. Thus, for example, potassium ferricyanide and hexamine both crystallise out from water in the anhydrous state. But when mixed together, they form the addition compound of the formula $K_3Fe(CN)_6 \cdot C_6H_{12}N_4 \cdot 9H_2O$. If we assume that the water molecules are attached to the positive ion, the point of attachment of the hexamine molecules becomes indefinite. It cannot be attached to the central atom of the anion which is co-ordinatively saturated. Barbieri, (*loc. cit.*) therefore, suggests that the hexamine molecules do not associate directly with the anions or cations, but combine with the salt by an indirect secondary valency in the sense meant by Werner and Weinland. Nor there is any justification to assume that the water molecules are attached to the positive ion or even to the hexamine molecule, as both the original salt and urotropine are anhydrous. Similar arguments apply equally to the cases of other compounds, where the addition of hexamine raises the water content of the product. The only plausible interpretation under these circumstances is that the hexamine molecules, which very likely possess fairly well developed dipole moments like ammonia, are held by electrostatic attraction to the positive and negative ions of the salt. This may, under certain circumstances, give rise to an alteration in the electrical field around the ions, whereby their capacity for associating dipole molecules of water is increased. In other words, both hexamine and water molecules are held simply by electrostatic attraction of the ions of the salt; no secondary valency of directional character, consisting of shared electrons as suggested by some, takes any part in the formation of these molecular or additive compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Compounds of Urotropine with Simple and Double Salts of Thiosulphato-pentacyano-cobaltic Acid.

Barium salt and urotropine.—A moderately strong solution of hexamethylene tetramine was added drop by drop to a concentrated solution of thiosulphato-pentacyano barium cobaltate with constant stirring in the cold (0°). Beautiful golden yellow crystals readily separated out. The crystals were filtered, washed with 10% urotropine solution and then with aqueous alcohol (1:1), and finally with

absolute alcohol. These were then dried in the air. The crystals readily dissolve in water giving orange coloured solution. (Found: N, 17.54; Ba, 31.12; Co, 6.93. $\text{Ba}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $1.5(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $4.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 17.77; Ba, 31.7; Co, 6.8 per cent).

Strontium salt and urotropine.—A slight excess of saturated solution of hexamine was added little by little with constant stirring to the solution of strontium salt of the complex cobaltic acid. The compound was obtained as a yellowish crystalline precipitate which was then drained, washed and dried as in the previous case. The crystals are very soluble in water, and, when examined under the microscope, appear as rectangular prisms and bars. (Found: N, 20.46; Co, 6.7; Sr, 19.86. $\text{Sr}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 20.63; Co, 6.7; Sr, 19.86 per cent).

Calcium salt and urotropine.—The substance was prepared from a saturated solution of the calcium salt and a moderately concentrated solution of hexamine in the same way as the previous compounds. The pale yellow crystals separating were filtered, washed and dried as before. The crystals are very soluble in water and appear as plates and crosses under the microscope. (Found: N, 22.28; Ca, 10.01; Co, 7.33. $\text{Ca}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 22.63; Ca, 9.94; Co, 7.33 per cent).

Magnesium salt and urotropine.—The substance was prepared from a concentrated solution of thiosulphato-pentacyano magnesium cobaltate and a moderately strong solution of urotropine as in the case of previous compounds. The double compound was obtained as a light-yellow crystalline precipitate. The crystals were washed and dried as usual. (Found: N, 21.5; Co, 6.99; Mg, 5.85. $\text{Mg}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 21.41; Co, 6.94; Mg, 5.75 per cent).

Lithium salt and urotropine.—The thiosulphato-pentacyano lithiumcobaltate was dissolved in the least amount of water. It was cooled in ice, then to this was added drop by drop a saturated solution of urotropine with constant stirring until the hexamine was in slight excess. The mixture was afterwards treated with 2-3 drops of alcohol. The crystals separated were drained, washed at first with 50 % alcohol, then with absolute alcohol and finally dried in air. The light-yellow crystalline substance appears as bushes of needles under the microscope. (Found: N, 24.27; Co, 7.75; Li, 3.78. $\text{Li}_4[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 24.2; Co, 7.83; Li, 3.81 per cent).

Barium potassium salt and urotropine.—A saturated solution of thiosulphato-pentacyano potassium cobaltate (6 g.) was mixed with requisite amount of barium chloride (1.28 g.) and a little potassium chloride (0.2 g) solution. On adding urotropine solution to the mixture, while constantly stirring, a light-yellow crystalline substance separated. It was drained, washed with aqueous urotropine (5%) until free from chloride, then with 5% alcohol and lastly with absolute alcohol. The substance was finally dried in air. It is less soluble in water than the pure barium compound. When examined under the microscope, it was found to consist of octahedral crystals. (Found: N, 20.57; Ba, 18.28; Co, 7.85; K, 10.33. $\text{BaK}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $1.5(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 20.45; Ba, 18.2; Co, 7.83; K, 10.36 per cent).

Strontium potassium salt and urotropine.—Thiosulphato-pentacyano potassium cobaltate (3 g.), strontium chloride (0.5 g.) and a little potassium chloride were dissolved in the least quantity of water. The solution was then treated drop by drop with a concentrated solution of hexamine in slight excess. Yellow crystals of the double compound separated at once. These were filtered, washed and dried as in the previous case. The crystals appeared octahedral in shape under the microscope. (Found: N, 23.2; Co, 8.72; K, 11.55; Sr, 12.94. $\text{SrK}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $1.5(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 22.8; Co, 8.71; K, 11.52; Sr, 12.94 per cent).

Calcium potassium salt and urotropine.—Calcium chloride (1 g.), the complex potassium salt (5 g.), and potassium chloride (0.5 g.) were dissolved in the least quantity of water. The mixture was placed in ice, and urotropine solution was added to it drop by drop with constant stirring until it was in slight excess. Light yellow crystals separated at once. It was filtered, washed and dried as before. The crystals, under the microscope, appear as rhombohedral plates. (Found: N, 18.54; Ca, 5.9; Co, 8.66; K, 11.45. $\text{CaK}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 18.4; Ca, 5.83; Co, 8.61; K, 11.38 per cent).

Magnesium potassium salt and urotropine.—The complex potassium salt (4 g.) was dissolved in the least amount of water; requisite amount of MgSO_4 (1 g.) and a little KCl (0.5 g.) were added to this solution. The cooled solution was mixed with urotropine while being constantly stirred. The substance separated out in yellow crystals. These were then dried and washed as before. The crystals appear as bushes of needles under the microscope.

(Found: N, 24.73; Co, 8.04; K, 10.62; Mg, 3.53. $\text{MgK}_2 [(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 24.97; Co, 8.08; K, 10.7; Mg, 3.83 per cent).

Lithium potassium salt and urotropine.—A mixture of 5.4 g. of thiosulphato-pentacyano potassium cobaltate, 0.12 g. of lithium chloride and 0.5 g. of potassium chloride was dissolved in the least amount of water and filtered. The clear filtrate was treated in the cold with a concentrated solution of urotropine in slight excess. The yellow crystalline precipitate formed was filtered, washed and dried as usual. The crystals appeared under the microscope octahedral in shape. (Found: N, 26.67; Co, 8.83; K, 11.49; Li, 2.03. $\text{Li}_2\text{K}_2 [(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 27.0; Co, 8.76; K, 11.59; Li, 2.08 per cent).

Barium ammonium salt and urotropine.—The complex ammonium salt (4 g.), BaCl_2 (0.5 g.) and NH_4Cl (0.2 g.) were dissolved in the least amount of water. The mixture was cooled in ice and mixed with a little excess of a concentrated solution of hexamine with constant stirring. Beautiful golden yellow crystals separated readily. These were filtered, washed and dried as in the previous cases. The compound is very soluble in water, and appears as prismatic rods under the microscope. (Found: N, 23.71; Ba, 17.95; Co, 7.75. $\text{Ba}(\text{NH}_4)_2 [(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $1.5(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $4.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 23.71; Ba, 17.94; Co, 7.71 per cent).

Strontium ammonium salt and urotropine.—The substance was prepared in the same way as the previous compounds from the complex ammonium salt, ammonium chloride, strontium chloride and hexamine. The substance, which consists of light yellow crystals, is extremely soluble in water, and appears under the microscope as rhombic plates. (Found: N, 26.74; Co, 8.74; Sr, 12.88. $\text{Sr}(\text{NH}_4)_2 [(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $1.5(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 27.1; Co, 8.80; Sr, 13.05 per cent).

Calcium ammonium salt and urotropine.—The compound was prepared from the complex ammonium salt, ammonium chloride, calcium chloride and urotropine in a way similar to that of the previous compound. The light-yellow crystals obtained were washed and dried as usual. Under the microscope the crystals appear octahedral in shape. (Found: N, 23.91; Ca, 6.20; Co, 8.96. $\text{Ca}(\text{NH}_4)_2 [(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$, $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 23.95; Ca, 6.22; Co, 9.12 per cent).

Magnesium ammonium salt and urotropine.—The substance was prepared from the complex ammonium salt, magnesium sulphate, ammonium sulphate and urotropine. The details of the preparation are identical with those of the previous compound. The yellow crystals obtained were filtered, washed and dried as before. These appear to consist of tetragonal plates under the microscope. (Found: N, 27.32; Co, 8.85; Mg, 3.66. $\text{Mg}(\text{NH}_4)_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$, $1.5(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 27.53; Co, 8.92; Mg, 3.67 per cent).

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